

APPRECIATIVE PROJECT DESIGN ORIENTATION AND ORPHANED LEARNERS' EDUCATIONAL ACHIEVEMENTS: PERSPECTIVES OF CARE GIVERS IN HOMA BAY COUNTY, KENYA

Abuya Isaac Odhiambo

Department of Open Learning,
University of Nairobi,
Kenya

Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to examine the perspectives of care givers on the influence of appreciative project design orientation on the educational achievements of orphaned learners enrolled in orphan support projects in Homa County, Kenya. The cross-sectional study was grounded on pragmatism. A total of 363 care givers participated in the study. Care Givers' Survey Questionnaire was used to collect data. To ensure validity and reliability of the research instrument, pilot testing was conducted in a community based orphan support project in the neighbouring Kisumu County. Cronbach alpha at $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance was used to compute the reliability coefficient of the pre-test instruments. Simple, multiple linear regressions and Pearson Correlation Coefficient models were used. Tests of statistical assumptions were carried out before data analysis to avoid invalidation of statistical analysis. One hypothesis was tested at $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance. The null hypothesis (H_0 : Appreciative Project Design Orientation does not significantly influence Orphaned Learners' Educational Achievements in Homa Bay County) was rejected since ($F(10,353) = 11.1945.265$, P -Value < 0.05 ; and so it was safe to suggest that at least one of the explanatory variables is significantly related to the Orphaned Learners' Educational Achievements. It is recommended that orphan support projects should integrate and intensify the use of appreciative project design orientation approaches to ensure sustainable educational achievements for orphaned learners. Since this study delimited itself to orphaned learners' educational achievements, further research should be carried out to examine the extent to which appreciative project design orientation influence the educational achievements of orphaned learners' test scores in examinable subjects.

Keywords: appreciative project design orientation, orphaned learners' educational achievements, care givers

1. Introduction

It is estimated that 145 million children below 18 years have lost one or both parents (UNICEF, 2008b). Worldwide, 15 million school age children have been orphaned due to AIDS, with 11.6 million of these children orphaned in sub-Saharan Africa alone orphaned due to AIDS. It is also estimated that 2.5 million of these orphaned children live in Kenya, with Homa Bay County having the highest number of orphans, due to high incidences of adult AIDS related mortality (UNICEF, 2008b). Available research suggests that orphaned learners have poor educational outcomes compared to non-orphaned learners. Apart from the emotional and psychological effects that losing a parent can have on learners, there is clear evidence that orphaned learners do not attend school regularly, and are dropping out of school at higher rate than non-orphaned children. Current knowledge suggests that when a parent dies, the amount of resources available for education decreases, as the cost of education becomes unaffordable, further compromising the rights of the orphaned learners to education.

For learners whose parents have died as result of AIDS, the stigma and discrimination within the families, communities and schools may further exacerbate poor educational outcomes for such learners, manifested in irregular school attendance, limited participation in co-curricular activities, reduced motivation for home work, and may contribute to discipline referrals and grade repetition, or might out rightly lead to such learners dropping out school (UNICEF, 2008b). Available research suggest that school attendance, participation in co-curricular activities, school discipline, homework completion and grade progression are critical indicators of educational achievements, and that these indicators positively influence performance in examinations.

Education is a basic human right for all children, including orphans, as recognised in the Convention on the Rights of the Child. It has been argued that a child who has access to quality primary education has a better chance in life. Basic quality education is also critically important to orphaned learners' social integration and psycho-social well-being. Access to quality and sustainable basic education at the primary school level helps orphaned learners affected by the trauma of parental death to regain a sense of normalcy and to recover from the psychosocial impacts of their experiences and disrupted lives (UNICEF, 2008b).. As well as benefiting individuals, education benefits whole nations as a major instrument for social and economic development. Particularly at the basic level, education is a major contributor to the reduction of poverty. Education increases labour productivity, improves health, and enables people to participate fully in the economy and the development of their societies. Poor educational outcomes for orphaned learners compromises the orphaned learners' quality of life, productivity and competitiveness in the labour market, thus further reinforcing the disadvantage of such orphaned learners.

To show commitments and support to the education of orphans, Kenya signed and supported the Declaration of the Right of the Child to Education, and has prioritized the education of orphaned learners, by investing financial and technical support towards the design and implementation of orphan support projects. It has been

argued that the success of orphan support projects depends on the extent to which they appreciate, empower, include and engage orphaned learners and the extent to which they promote the education of orphaned learners. The psychological and physical trauma following parental death, may affect the self-esteem of these orphaned learners. These learners are likely to feel unappreciated, disempowered, excluded and disengaged in the learning process. As a result, for the orphan support projects to function effectively and to deliver services to the orphaned learners, the projects have to appreciate the challenges and diversity of orphaned learners, and must ensure that their policies and services are inclusive, empowering and should promote the engagement of the orphaned learners in the learning process.

Appreciative project design orientation, conceptualised as project design approach that appreciates, recognises and positively affirms orphaned learners (Shier, 2001), is believed to have beneficial influence on a wide range of educational outcomes amongst orphaned learners (UNICEF, 2008b). Orphaned learners in Kenya do not attend school regularly, compared to non-orphaned pupils in the country (Evans and Miguel, 2007), since the death of a parent or parents adversely affects the support that these children could have received from their parents. The stigmatization and discrimination of orphaned learners, and the poor educational achievements among orphaned learners in Kenya led to calls for appreciative orphan support projects ((UNICEF, 2008b). The critical role that appreciation plays in the educational achievements of learners was demonstrated by Bergmark and Alerby (2008) in their phenomenological study of the lived experiences of learners in Swedish secondary schools with ethical situations. The study found that appreciative educational environments characterised by healthy and positively affirming relationships between the teachers and the learners improved the speech and action and power among the learners, with demonstrated positive ethical decision making among the learners which led to improved educational outcomes for the learners. This study confirmed the positive effective of appreciation and positive relationships between learners: appreciation of learners and positive affirmation of the learners lead to improved ethical decision making and improved perception that the learners that they are in control of their learning.

2. Statement of the Problem

It is estimated that about 2.5 million learners in Kenya have been orphaned by AIDS. Homa Bay County has the highest HIV prevalence, adult related AIDS related mortality and AIDS orphaned learners orphaned in Kenya. AIDS is a highly stigmatized condition and learners believed to have been orphaned by AIDS are more stigmatised and discriminated against. The stigmatization and discrimination of learners' presumed to have been orphaned by AIDS, adversely affect the orphaned learners' educational achievements. Due to the stigmatization and discrimination, learners presumed to have been orphaned by AIDS are more likely not to attend school, less likely to participate in co-curricular activities, more likely to repeat class, are likely to have low motivation to

do homework and may engage in socially undesirable behaviours like drug taking and engaging in risky sexual behaviours, with adverse effects and consequences on the learners' human capital development, competitiveness and employability.

The reduced human capital development, competitiveness and employability among orphaned learners with poor educational outcomes may exacerbate the orphaned learners' risks and vulnerability, thus sustaining the vicious cycle of poverty among the orphaned learners. Such orphaned learners are more likely than their non-orphaned peers to engage in risky behaviours that may predispose them to the risk of HIV and AIDS, leading to high morbidity and increased mortality among the orphaned learners, with negative impacts on economy, the society and the nation as a whole. The poor human capital development among orphaned learners may put further strain on Kenya's economy, thus increasing further the cost of orphan support projects.

It has been argued that orphaned learners' educational achievements may be improved through cost effective project design orientations that appreciate the orphaned learners. It is believed that learners, who are appreciated, are likely to attend school regularly, actively participate in co-curricular activities, be more disciplined and do homework regularly, thus improving their overall educational achievements. Improving the educational achievements among orphaned learners by investing in appreciative project design orientation is cost effective, and is likely to reduce the cost of providing educational support for orphaned learners in the country, in the face of dwindling government and donor support for orphan support projects.

The available evidence on the influence of appreciative project design orientation has been conducted in non-project settings with non-orphaned learners. Moreover, these studies have not taken the perspectives of care givers, who spend time with orphaned learners, into consideration. Studies on care givers have mostly focused on the care giving challenges including the burnout and the pressures that care givers experience. Care givers are best placed to understand how the orphan support projects are affecting the orphaned children under their care. As the support from donors and governments for orphan support projects in Kenya face uncertain future due to high inflation and donor fatigue, it has been argued that appreciation may improve orphaned learners' educational achievements. However, no known studies have been conducted in orphan support projects to examine the perspectives of the care givers on the extent to which appreciative project design orientation influence educational achievements of the orphaned learners under their care.

2.1 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine the perspectives of care givers on the influence of appreciative project design orientation on the educational achievements of orphaned learners enrolled in orphan support projects in Homa Bay County, Kenya.

2.2 Research Hypothesis

The study tested only one null hypothesis: H₀1: Appreciative project design orientation does not significantly influence orphaned learners' educational achievements in Homa Bay County.

3. Review of Related Literature

This section reviews the empirical literature on the influence of appreciative project design orientation and the empirical literature on learners' educational achievements and on learners' educational achievements.

3.1 Appreciative Project Design Orientation and Educational Achievements

Appreciative project design orientation, conceptualised as project design approach that appreciates, recognises and positively affirms disadvantaged and vulnerable children (Shier, 2001), is believed to have beneficial influence on a wide range of outcomes, including educational outcomes for disadvantaged and vulnerable children, like the orphaned learners (Shier, 2001; UNICEF, 2008b). There is emerging evidence that appreciative projects foster and improve participation of disadvantaged and vulnerable learners, which lead to improved educational achievements and learning outcomes for these learners. The critical role that appreciation plays in the educational achievements of learners was also demonstrated by Bergmark and Alerby (2008) in their phenomenological study of the lived experiences of learners in Swedish secondary schools with ethical situations. The study found that appreciative educational environments characterised by healthy and positively affirming relationships between the teachers and the learners improved the speech and action and power among the learners, with demonstrated positive ethical decision making among the learners which led to improved educational outcomes for the learners. This study confirmed the positive effective of appreciation and positive relationships between learners: appreciation of learners and positive affirmation of the learners lead to improved ethical decision making and improved perception that the learners that they are in control of their learning.

The positive influence of appreciation and recognition on the educational achievements of learners was also demonstrated in a study by Abildsnes *et al.*, (2015). The study found that the positive thoughts among teachers and nurses on the capability of learners significantly improved the participation of the learners in physical education and also in the class. The study was conducted to explore the effects of positive thoughts of physical education teachers and school nurses on participation of learners in physical education and their participation in class. The appreciation and the positive affirmation of the learners, who had hitherto been perceived as unable, fostered and improved the self-esteem of the learners, which led to their success in both physical education (which some had thought the learners could not manage) and their improved participation in the class. This study confirmed the beneficial effects of appreciation and recognition on learners' educational achievements.

Hallinan (2008) investigated the role of teachers in shaping learners' feelings about school. The unique role that teachers play relative to learners and the kinds of experiences that teachers create for learners suggest that teachers may exert a powerful influence on whether learners like school. Since attachment to school has been shown to affect learners' academic performance, identifying the characteristics of teachers that have a positive effect on learners' feelings about school is one way to increase learners' academic achievement. The study estimated cross-sectional and longitudinal models of teachers' influences on learners' feelings about school on data from 6th-, 8th- and 10th-grade learners in public and Catholic schools in Chicago. It found that learners who perceive that their teachers care about them, respect them, and praise them are more apt to like school than are those who do not, but that teachers' expectations for learners' achievement have a negligible effect on whether learners like school.

Stringer and Hurt (1981) hypothesized that positive verbal reinforcement (praise) leads to improved educational achievements, while also holding the view that that praise can be a threat for a child rather than a reward. The researchers conducted a study to investigate the factors to consider before utilizing praise as a reinforcing device. Results indicate that praise results in improved achievement only when it is congruent with learner needs. Researchers are examining the relationship between praise and behavior, with studies indicating that praise reinforces appropriate classroom behavior and inappropriate behavior can best be controlled by ignoring it rather than punishing it. The study also suggests that learners are intrinsically motivated when they engage in behavior because the behavior itself is rewarding. Adding extrinsic reinforcement to an already interesting task does not increase motivation but may instead cause a student to lose interest.

Pomerantz and Kempner (2013) examined if mothers' day-to-day praise of children's success in school plays a role in children's theory of intelligence and motivation. Participants were 120 children (mean age = 10.23 years) and their mothers who took part in a 2-wave study spanning 6 months. During the first wave, mothers completed a 10-day daily interview in which they reported on their use of person (e.g., "You are smart") and process (e.g., "You tried hard") praise. Children's entity theory of intelligence and preference for challenge in school were assessed with surveys at both waves. Mothers' person, but not process, praise was predictive of children's theory of intelligence and motivation: The more person praise mothers used, the more children subsequently held an entity theory of intelligence and avoided challenge over and above their earlier functioning on these dimensions.

Skipper and Douglas (2015) conducted an experimental study to examine the impact of praise and positive feedback on learners' perceptions of the student-teacher relationship among a sample of 145 aged 9-11 British learners in experiment 1 and among a sample of 98 aged 7-11 British learners in experiment 2. In experiment 1, participants read three scenarios where they succeeded and received one of two types of praise (person or process) or no praise. Participants then read two scenarios where they failed. In experiment 2, participants read that they had failed in three tasks and received one of two types of criticism (person or process) or no criticism. Participants

then read two scenarios where they succeeded. They rated how much they liked the teacher and how much they felt that the teacher liked them. Results show that learners felt more positive about the student-teacher relationship following success than failure. Type of praise did not influence perceptions of the student-teacher relationship following success or failure. However, person criticism led children to view the student-teacher relationship more negatively following failure and maintain this negative view following the first success.

Robinson (2014) conducted a qualitative study on the effects of positive and self-affirmations on stereotype threat and optimism among teachers. A central finding from this case study is that self-affirmation writing sustained the teacher candidates through the challenges they encountered during their field experience teaching. The research participants describe how self-affirmations helps them focus on their own positive inner voice, or whispering self, that encourages self-acceptance and a belief that they are good persons who care for themselves and others. Additionally, candidates apply, or envision how they might apply self-affirmation writing exercises in their own middle and high school classrooms.

Howell, Caldarella, Korth and Young (2014) investigated the relationship between praise and student classroom behavior and relationships in schools. Results indicated that participants believed praise helped improve classroom behavior, relationships, and home-school communication. Results also suggested that praise was sustainable and had a good level of teacher buy-in.

To investigate the effects of feedback on performance and factors associated with it, Lipnevich and Smith (2009), carried out an experiment involving college learners (N = 464) working on an essay examination under 3 conditions: no feedback, detailed feedback that was perceived by participants to be provided by the course instructor, and detailed feedback that was perceived by participants to be computer generated. Additionally, these conditions were crossed with factors of grade (receiving a numerical grade or not) and praise (receiving a statement of praise or not). The task under consideration was a single-question essay examination administered at the beginning of the course. Detailed feedback on the essay, specific to individual's work, was found to be strongly related to student improvement in essay scores, with the influence of grades and praise being more complex. Generally, receipt of a tentative grade depressed performance, although this effect was ameliorated if accompanied by a statement of praise. Overall, detailed, descriptive feedback was found to be most effective when given alone, unaccompanied by grades or praise. It was also found that the perceived source of the feedback (the computer or the instructor) had little impact on the results.

Alcott (2017) examined the influence of teacher encouragement on learners' educational progress, using data from the Longitudinal Study of Young People in England (LSYPE). The researcher used propensity-score matching to investigate whether encouragement influences the likelihood of learners enrolling in (1) advanced high school (A-level) courses and (2) a university degree course. Model estimates suggest that encouragement does have a significant positive impact on both outcomes. In addition, the researcher investigated whether encouragement effects vary according

to parental education and the given student's prior academic achievement. The finding suggests that the impact is greatest for those learners in the middle third of academic achievement as well as those with lower levels of parental education.

Khan, Ahmad, Hamdan and Mustaffa (2014) examined the predictors of academic achievement: role of parenting styles, educational encouragement, gender and ethnicity among special education learners. Participants of this study consisted 200 special education learners (N = 105 boys and N = 95 girls) age varies 14 to 19 years from one school located at Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia. Results showed authoritative parenting styles were mostly used by the parents of their special education learners. Significant relationships were existed in parenting styles, educational encouragement and academic achievement among special educational learners. Educational encouragement from mother, father, sibling and friends, ethnicity and gender were found to be significant predictors for academic achievement.

3.2 Learners' Educational Achievements

The educational achievements reviewed under this section include school attendance, participation in co-curricular activities, homework completion, and learner discipline. Empirical studies on these indicators of educational achievements are reviewed. While a number of studies focus on the test score as the most critical indicator of educational performance, we feel strongly that the indicators we have reviewed have a direct bearing on test scores and we strongly believe that they should be seen not as determinants of academic achievements, but as indicators of educational achievements.

The impact of educational reforms in India on school attendance among low income rural school learners aged 6-11 in India was evaluated by Datta Gupta, Dubey and Simonsen (2018). The researchers estimated a triple difference model allowing for differential (linear) trends and found a positive causal effect of school reforms on the school attendance rate of rural low-income children, although somewhat stronger for girls than boys. For both girls and boys in these groups, the increase in attendance rate was driven by the 6–11 age categories and by children of scheduled tribe or scheduled caste background.

Cosgrove, Chen and Castelli (2018) examined the relationship of grit as a construct representing perseverance to overcoming barriers and the total number of school absences to academic performance (AP) while controlling for sociodemographics, fitness and Body Mass Index (BMI). Adolescents (N = 397, SD = 1.85; 80.9% females; 77.1% Hispanic) from an urban, minority-majority city in the Southern United States completed the FitnessGram® assessment of physical fitness (e.g., aerobic capacity and Body Mass Index (BMI)) and the valid and reliable short grit survey. The schools provided sociodemographics, attendance, and AP data for the adolescents. The results showed that Adolescents with higher grit scores ($r_s=0.21$, $P < 0.001$) and less total absences ($r_s=-0.35$, $P < 0.001$) performed better on AP. Hierarchical multiple regression indicated that grit and absences were associated with AP ($\beta = 0.13$, $P < 0.01$ and $\beta = -0.35$, $P < 0.001$). Grit and a total number of absences are significant contributors to academic success, particularly among Hispanic adolescents.

The relations between family income, as measured by receipt of free or reduced-price lunch, school attendance, and academic achievement among a diverse sample of children from kindergarten to 4th grade ("N" = 35,419) was examined by Morrissey, Hutchison and Winsler (2014)) using both random and within-child fixed-effects models. The results suggest that the receipt of free or reduced-price lunch and duration of receipt have small but positive associations with school absences and tardiness. Poor attendance patterns predict poorer grades, with absences more associated with grades than tardiness. Given the small associations between receipt of free or reduced-price lunch and school attendance, and between the duration of receipt of free or reduced-price lunch and children's grades, results do not provide strong evidence that absences and tardiness meaningfully attenuate relations between the duration of low family income and student achievement; poorer attendance and persistent low income independently predict poorer grades.

Sakiz (2017) reported the outcomes of a school-based programme aiming to promote achievement, attendance and positive perceptions towards the school climate and social-emotional adaptation among learners with disabilities (SWD). The programme included a series of training and social activities for school staff, parents and children followed by implementation of the knowledge gained through these activities. The programme lasted one school year and data were collected through quantitative and qualitative methods. Results of the study indicated enhanced student attendance and achievement, social-emotional development, and positive perceptions about the school climate. In addition, parents and teachers were mostly content with development of learners and the attempts of their schools to prompt student learning. Findings of this research indicate the significance of the holistic approach in educating SWD in mainstream schools and confirm that schools can make progress relying on their internal structures and planned action.

Participation in co-curricular activities has been considered as a critical determinant of educational achievements. Yokley-Busby (2013) assessed the impact of school attendance longevity participation in an after school program, attending one and two times or three times weekly for two years, designed to build intentional relationships and support academic success, on urban elementary school learners' achievement, attendance, and positive school awards was investigated. School attendance as measured by total end of the fifth-grade year overall absence totals were not statistically different where $F(2, 27) = 0.65$, $p = 0.530$. Findings suggest that even limited student participation after school program resulted in achievement, attendance, and earned awards consistent with the study's control group learners who were not in need of these after school services.

Streb (2009) carried out a study to determine the academic achievement of learners who are involved in co-curricular when statistically compared to the performance of their peers who are not involved in co-curricular activities. The scope of the investigation only included high school learners and the relationship between their involvement in activities and their academic performance. In addition, it does differentiate between the types of co-curricular activities a student is involved in, be it

sports or performing groups, or even after-school clubs. Although there are many instruments used to measure student achievement, this study relied on two commonly utilized and universally accepted methods; ACT scores and Grade Point Averages. Much of the research into co-curricular activity participation by High School learners suggests that such pursuits have a positive correlation with improved academic achievement. The research conducted in this study supports previous studies which showed that participation in co-curricular activities had a positive association with learners' academic achievement. In this study, 492 graduating seniors were surveyed regarding their four year participation in after-school programs. Academic success measure of ACT scores and GPA were used in the data analysis of these learners.

The relationship between participation in co-curricular activities and academic performance measured by grade-point averages and persistence measured by continued enrollment was examined by Pillar (2016) among 690 sophomore learners who entered a small private institution at the beginning of the 2013-2014 academic years. The researcher analyzed relationships among sophomore participation in co-curricular activities and academic performance measured by grade-point averages. Significant relationships were found among sophomore student participation in co-curricular activities, organizational type, academic success, and persistence. Statistical analyses indicated that participation in co-curricular activities led to increased enrollment by sophomore learners in their junior years. Further findings revealed that resident learners participated in co-curricular activities at higher rates and were also more likely to persist.

Jenkins (2009) used logistical regression and ordinary least squares to examine factors that contribute to the narrowing of the achievement gap at an urban high school in the Midwest. The study analyzed the relationship between five independent variables related to participation in co-curricular activities, demographic characteristics of individual learners, and four dependent variables related to academic achievement at a large urban high school in the Midwest. The independent variables included the following: major, minor, and non-participation in co-curricular activities, student background, and socioeconomic status. In this study, academic achievement was defined by high school class rank, grade point average, whether a student took the ACT exam and performance on the ACT exam. A database of 1,440 learners who graduated over a four year period from the large urban Midwestern high school between 2003 and 2006 was utilized. Major participation in co-curricular activities had a statistically significant and positive influence on grade point average, high school class rank percentile, and performance on the ACT exam. However, co-curricular participation was not found to have a statistically significant influence on the probability that a student takes the ACT exam.

The impact of organizational and motivational strategies on homework completion among high school learners was examined by Anliker, Aydt, Kellams and Rothlisberger (1997). The problem of homework completion was evidenced by existing grade and homework reports and teacher and student surveys. The strategy used to encourage learners to complete homework through enhancing their organizational

skills was a teacher-issued standard homework assignment notebook that served as a visual reminder of the homework assignments and their value. An individual student-generated grade record was also incorporated into the intervention, thereby increasing learners' responsibility for grade performance and knowledge. Procedures for failure to turn in homework, pink slips, were established with the learners, reinforcing again their responsibility for their academic achievement. Data on the impact of the intervention were collected through weekly teacher journals, comparison of the homework completion rate of comparable classes the previous year, pre-intervention surveys for parents and teachers, and pre- and post-intervention surveys for learners. Post-intervention data indicated an increase in the homework completion rate. A positive change in student attitude toward the importance of homework for academic success was evident in the post-intervention student surveys. There was also an increase in use of school time to complete homework assignments.

Brender (1996) investigated the effects of homework completion on test scores for 401 undergraduate learners, 94 percent African American, at an urban university in 2 levels of introductory Spanish, all with the same instructor. Five to six teacher-generated exams were administered during the course; the lowest test score for each student was discarded. Fairly consistent bell curves were noted for almost every class on virtually every test. Homework consisted of lengthy workbook assignments of 8-11 pages due the day of the chapter exam and short daily assignments of approximately one page; homework was reviewed at the beginning of each class. Although the text was changed four times, median test scores changed little with the different texts. Results indicate statistically significant correlations between homework completion rates and test scores based on class level. A strong correlation was found in the 101-level classes to support Keith's (1988, 1992) research suggesting a stronger correlation between achievement and homework for African Americans, although the reverse was noted in 102-level classes.

Brender (1996) investigated the relationship between learners' completion of homework assignments, both brief and lengthy, and student achievement on five to six teacher-developed exams administered during the semester among 401 Chicago State University (Illinois) undergraduate learners in elementary Spanish courses. The study spanned six semesters. Results show some statistically significant positive correlations between homework completion rates and test scores based on class level. It was also discovered that learners in the Spanish 101 course were much less likely than learners in the Spanish 102 course to complete their homework. Degree of difficulty of the courses is illustrated in the difference in median tests scores, which were lower in the second-semester group. No significant conclusion could be drawn about the relationship of race, homework completion, and test scores. Overall, it is concluded that learners who complete homework achieve better test scores.

Lynch, Theodore, Bray and Kehle (2009) employed an alternating-treatments design to compare the differential effect of group contingencies on the improvement of homework completion and accuracy of learners with disabilities in a self-contained fifth-grade classroom. Generally, past investigations have indicated a positive

association between homework performance and academic achievement. Relative to their nondisabled peers, learners with learning disabilities are more at risk for homework problems. Thus, homework assignments are particularly important for learners with disabilities to reinforce learning and improve academic achievement. The results suggested that all group contingencies were effective in enhancing overall completion and accuracy, with no substantial differences evidenced by one contingency in particular.

Núñez, Suárez, Rosário, Vallejo, Valle and Epstein (2015) examined the relationship between perceived parental homework involvement (i.e., parental homework control and parental homework support), student homework behaviors (i.e., time spend on homework completion, time management, and amount of homework completed), and student academic achievement. Using Mplus5.1, a structural equation model was fit for 1683 learners at different stages of schooling (i.e., elementary school--5th and 6th grades; junior high school--7th and 8th grades; and high school--9th and 10th grades). The data showed that student homework behaviors, perceived parental homework involvement, and academic achievement are significantly related. However, results vary depending on the learners' grade level: (a) in junior high and high school, perceived parental homework involvement is related to learners' homework behaviors, but not in elementary school; and (b) although learners' homework behaviors are related to academic achievement at each school level, the direction and magnitude of the relationships vary. Specifically, the relationship between perceived parental homework involvement and academic achievement is stronger in junior high and high school than in elementary school; and student homework behaviors mediate the association between perceived parental homework involvement (control and support) and academic achievement only in junior high and high school.

The influence of homework experiences on learners' academic grades was studied by Kitsantas and Zimmerman (2009) with 223 college learners. Learners' self-efficacy for learning and perceived responsibility beliefs were included as mediating variables in this research. The learners' homework influenced their achievement indirectly via these two self-regulatory beliefs as well as directly. Self-efficacy for learning, although moderately correlated with perceptions of responsibility, predicted course grades more strongly than the latter variable. No gender differences were found for any of the variables, a finding that extends prior research based on high school girls. Educational implications about the importance of learners' homework completion and its relationship to college learners' development of self-regulation and positive self-efficacy beliefs is discussed from a social cognitive perspective.

Blackfelner and Ranallo (1998) demonstrated that parent involvement has many beneficial effects for learners. This action research project designed and implemented a program to raise the academic achievement of second-grade learners by increasing parent involvement. The learners attended two second-grade classrooms in a west-central Illinois school. The problem of low academic achievement in the classrooms was studied using anecdotal records, teacher observations, test scores, and records of homework completion. Analysis of the data indicated that many factors influenced

parent involvement, including: (1) parents' fear of school; (2) parents' lack of time; (3) parents' lack of transportation; and (4) parents' embarrassment about their own educational level. To increase parent involvement, a number of activities were developed, including: (1) daily use of a reflective journal by learners; (2) homework activities designed to check student and parent responsibility; (3) use of the school district's homework hotline phone system; (4) parent/child activity time at school, which was designed to acquaint parents with ways to help their children be more successful in school; (5) a newsletter; and (6) parent-teacher conferences. Surveys distributed at the end of the project indicated a positive change in parents' attitude toward communication between home and school, and that those who had volunteered felt good about the experience. Learners' scores on the posttest surveys showed a small improvement. (Sixteen appendices include parent and student surveys, homework activities, and parent invitations to school activities.

Simba, Agak and Kabuka (2016) carried out a study to determine the level of discipline and extent of impact of discipline on academic performance among class eight pupils in the sub-county's public primary schools. The study adopted descriptive survey and correlational research designs. The study population comprised 2,450 class eight pupils in the sub-county's public primary schools. From 34 randomly selected schools, 817 pupils were selected by stratified random sampling. Questionnaires were used to collect data on discipline and academic performance of the pupils. Reliability coefficients of the questionnaires were determined by test-retest method and found to be 0.83 and 0.97 for questionnaire on discipline and academic performance respectively. The questionnaires' face and content validity was ascertained by experts. Results indicated that 46 (5.6%), 214 (26.2%), 413 (50.6%) and 144 (17.6%) of the pupils had low, moderate, high, and very high discipline respectively. Also, discipline related positively with, and accounted for 23% of variance in the pupils' academic performance ($R = 0.480$, $\beta = 0.480$, $R^2 = 0.230$, $p < 0.05$). The study recommended enhancement of discipline among the pupils for improvement of their academic performance.

Schuck (2017) evaluated the effect of crime and discipline on graduation rates in higher education. Using national data on more than 1250 public and private non-profit institutions that were drawn from the Integrated Postsecondary Education Data System, the results reveal that more violence on and around campus is associated with lower 4-year graduation rates, whereas higher rates of disciplinary actions regarding alcohol, drugs, and weapons are associated with higher graduation rates. Furthermore, the findings suggest that utilizing the student conduct system rather than the criminal justice system to address minor offenses is more likely to lead to student success. This study contributes to the growing literature on college effectiveness and the influence of institutional structures and organizational policies on student achievement. The results of this study suggest that violent crime, institutional conduct systems, and campus police departments warrant further investigation.

Garo (2017) examined school outcomes for Black male secondary school learners in relation to neighborhood violence, focusing on Disproportionality in out of school suspension and below-proficiency achievement on selected standardized tests.

Grounded in trauma and strain theories, student aggressive response to violence is attributed in part to post-traumatic stress disorder as triggered by traumatic experience but also as anger and frustration over unjust treatment. The study hypothesized neighborhood violence as moderator between Black males and disparities among the selected outcomes as advocacy for trauma-sensitive practices in lieu of exclusionary discipline. Relative risk ratios calculated discipline and achievement disproportionality, while spatial and multi-level modeling methods examined statistical significant impacts of neighborhood violence exposure on student behavior (suspensions) and learning (test proficiency), considering also significance with individual, level-1 variables on special education, homelessness, arrest and unexcused absence. A neighborhood trauma vulnerability index (TVI), established via geographic information system, formed the level-2 variable in modeling of violence exposure on student outcomes.

Austin (2013) examined the influence of Effective Teens training on the attendance, discipline referrals, and academic achievement of 10th grade learners. The theoretical framework of the study was choice theory, which uses reality therapy to define how individuals may use thinking and evaluation to make pragmatic decisions. The theoretical basis for choice theory is that individuals are controlled by their needs and choose behaviors that meet the needs at that time. The research sample included 96 Grade 10 learners in 1 rural high school. A quasi-experimental, nonequivalent, pre- and post-test control group design was used to determine differences in the variables between the treatment and control groups. The independent variable was the presence or absence of a 3-week counselor-led activity based on the texts, "The 7 Habits of Highly Effective Teens" and "The 7 Habits of Highly Effective Teens Personal Workbook"; the dependent variables were attendance, discipline referrals, and academic achievement. An analysis of covariance revealed no significant differences in outcomes based on the treatment. Because counselors assist learners in focusing on academic, personal/social and career development, the literature suggested that providing learners with access to counselors in the school setting may impact social change for learners by encouraging academic success and the development of skills that allow them to lead fulfilling lives as responsible citizens.

4. Methodology

Cross-sectional research design was adopted in this study. Cross sectional design is based on observations made at one point in time (Kothari (1985). Cross-sectional design collects data in a single point in time from a sample drawn from a cross section of the population. The data was collected in a single point among project managers. The diverse geographical locations of the orphan support projects and target population made cross-sectional design appropriate for this study. The sample size for this study was drawn from a target population of 7043 Care givers from 20 support projects in Homa Bay County. Using Krecie and Morgan (1970) sample estimation table, a sample of 363 care givers was deemed to be sufficient for this study. Proportionate stratified

random sampling and was used to get a proportionate sample of care givers from the orphan support projects.

The main instrument for data collection in this study was self-administered questionnaire. The questionnaire for the care givers had three sections. Section A was on the demographic profiles of the care givers, Section B: Sought information on Appreciative Design Orientation, C sought information on Orphaned Learners' Educational Achievements. The statements on Sections B and C of the questionnaire used positively and negatively worded items as recommended by Williams (1974), Numally (1978) Baumgartner and Steenkemp (2001), Podsakoff, *et al.*, (2003) and Weijters and Baumgartner (2012). These authorities argued that the use of positively and negatively worded statements in a questionnaire minimise bias because such items reduce speed and promote cognitive reasoning in the subjects.

The self-administered Appreciative Project Design Orientation (ADO) Questionnaire contains five positively worded statements and five negatively worded statements to determine the extent to which the orphaned learners agreed with the appreciative design orientation statements. The appreciative statements are. ADO1: The orphaned learners are motivated by the project/ADO2: The orphaned learners are not motivated by the projects; ADO3: The orphaned learners are appreciated by the project/ADO4: The orphaned learners are not motivated by the project; ADO5: The orphaned learners are encouraged by the project/ ADO6: The orphaned learners are not encouraged by the project; ADO7: The orphaned learners are praised by the project/ ADO8: The orphaned learners are not praised by the project; ADO9: The orphaned learners are valued by the project/ADO10: The orphaned learners are not valued by the project. Each of the statements had a 5 Likert scale ranging from Strongly Disagree(SD)=1; Disagree (D)= 2; Neutral (N)-3; Agree (A)=4; and Strongly Agree (SA)=5 is used.

The Orphaned Learners' Educational Achievements Questionnaire (OLEA) contained five positively worded statements and five negatively worded statements to determine the extent to which the orphaned learners agreed with the statements on orphaned learners' educational achievements. The orphaned learners' educational achievements statements are: OLEA1-The orphaned learners attend school regularly/ OLEA2- The orphaned learners do not attend school regularly; OLEA3-The orphaned learners participate in co-curriculum activities/ OLEA4-The orphaned learners do not participate in co-curriculum activities; OLEA5-The orphaned learners behave well in school/ OLEA6- The orphaned learners do not behave well in school; OLEA7-The orphaned learners pass school examinations and get promoted to the next class/ OLEA8- The orphaned learners do not pass school examinations and get promoted to the next class; OLEA9- The orphaned learners always do their homework/ OLEA10-The orphaned learners do not always do their homework . Each of the statements had a 5 Likert scale ranging from Strongly Disagree(SD)=1; Disagree (D)= 2; Neutral (N)-3; Agree (A)=4; and Strongly Agree (SA)= 5 is used.

The research instrument was piloted at an Orphan Support Project in the neighbouring Kisumu among 9 orphan support project managers. As recommended by

Kothari (1985), a pre-test sample of a tenth of the total sample with homogenous characteristic was appropriate for a pilot study. Since the total number of the sampled care givers was 363, 36care givers were equivalent to 10% of the total sample of care givers. The research instruments also used appropriate grammar for all the respondents. The statements in the questionnaire were clear and precise. The research instruments were also reviewed by the supervisors who are experts in questionnaire design. The supervisors reviewed the questionnaires and made recommended on what was to be included and removed to ensure that the instruments were not ambiguous and difficult for all the respondents.

Quantitative data were analysed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS Version 21). The questionnaire items were checked for completeness and a follow up undertaken to ensure that lost and unanswered questionnaires were re-administered to ensure increased questionnaire response rate. Each and every questionnaire was given unique identifier codes to ensure confidentiality and anonymity of the respondents. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were analysed. Descriptive statistics such as means, standard deviations, frequencies and percentages counts were presented using frequency and percentage tables. Pearson Correlation Coefficients was computed to determine the association between the design orientation and educational achievement variables. Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) was applied to reflect degree of linear relationship between appreciative project design orientation and learners' achievements. The null hypotheses were tested at $\alpha=0.05$ level of significance.

A number of ethical issues were considered in this study. These included informed consent, confidentiality, right to privacy, respect for the participants' autonomy, honesty, and participants' right to discontinue. The participants were informed about the purpose and objectives of the study and asked to participate in the study. Only those participants who accepted to participate were involved in the study. No payments or any form of material or psychological inducements be use to entice the participants into the study.

5. Results

5.1 Care Givers' Demographic Profile

The demographic questionnaire for the care givers sought information on their age bracket, gender, marital status, number of orphaned learners they care for, number of years in taking care of orphaned learners and their highest educational qualifications.

Table 1: Care givers' Demographic Profile

Care Givers' Profile	Frequency	Percent (%)	Cumulative %
Age bracket			
18-25yrs	69	19.00	19.00
25-30yrs	37	10.19	29.19
30-35yrs	71	19.56	48.75
35-40yrs	64	17.63	66.38

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40-45yrs	19	5.23	71.61
45-50yrs	54	14.89	86.50
50-55 yrs	27	7.44	93.94
Above 55 yrs	22	6.06	100.0
Total	363	100.0	
Gender			
Male	65	17.91	17.91
Female	298	82.09	100
Total	363	100	
Marital status			
Married	152	41.87	41.87
Widowed	103	28.38	70.25
Divorced	55	15.15	85.40
Not Married	53	14.60	100
Total	363	100	
No. of Orphaned learners taken care of			
1-2	113	31.13	31.13
3-5	132	36.36	67.49
More than 5	118	32.51	100
Total	363	100	
No of years taking care of orphaned learners			
Less than 1 year	59	16.25	16.25
1-5 years	139	38.29	54.54
6-10 years	76	20.94	75.48
More than 10 years	89	24.52	100
Total	363	100	
Highest educational qualification			
Degree	34	9.37	9.37
Diploma	43	11.85	21.22
Secondary certificate	143	39.39	60.61
Primary certificate	143	39.39	100
Total	363	100	

Table 1 presents a summary of the demographic profile of the care givers. Out of the 363 sampled care givers, Majority of the care givers 69 (19.56%) were aged between 30-35 years; 69 (19.0%) of the care givers were aged between 18-25 years; 37 (10.19%) were aged between 25-30 years ;71 (19.56%) were between 30-35 years ;64 (17.63%) of the care givers were aged 35-40 years; 19 (5.23%) of the care givers were aged 40-45 years ; 54 (14.89%) of the care givers were aged 45-50 years; 27(7.44%) of the care givers were aged 50-55 years; while 22(6.06%) of the care givers were aged 55 years and above.

Majority 298 (82.09) of the care givers were female; while only 65 (17.91%) of the care givers were male. The findings on the gender distribution suggesting that the

burden of caring for orphaned learners placed on the women, which points to the feminization of caring for orphans in Homa Bay County. 152 (41.87%) of the care givers were married; 103 (28.38%) of the care givers were widowed; 55(15.15%) of the care givers were divorced while 53(14.6%) of the care givers were not married. The data suggests that married couples were more likely to take care of orphaned learners, pointing to relatively stable family care environments for the orphaned learners.

113(31.13%) care givers took care of between 1-2 orphaned learners; 132 (36.36%) of the care givers took care of between 3-5 orphaned learners; 118(32.51%) of the care givers took care of more 5 orphaned learners. The data on the number of orphans being taken care of points to the high number of orphans in Homa Bay County. 59(16.25%) of the care givers had less one year in taking care of orphaned learners, 139(38.29%) of the care givers had between 1-5 years' experience in taking care of orphaned learners; 76(20.94%) of the care givers had between 6-10 years while 89(24.52%) of the care givers had more than 10 years in taking care of orphaned learners. 34(9.37%) of the care givers had a degree, 43(11.85%) of the care givers had diploma; 143(39.39%) of the care givers had secondary school certificate and an equal number of 143(39.39%) of the care givers had primary school level certificate, indicating the relatively high literacy level among the care givers in the county.

5.2 Descriptive Analysis on Care Givers' Perspectives on Appreciative Design Orientation

Information was sought from the care givers on their perspectives on the influence of influence of Appreciative Design Orientation on Orphaned Learners' Educational Achievements. Table 2 present the findings on the perspective of care givers, descriptively.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics on Care Givers' Perspectives on Appreciative Project Design Orientation

	Statements on Appreciative Design Orientation (ADO)	SD(1) f (%)	D(2) f (%)	N(3) f (%)	A(4) f (%)	SA(5) f (%)	Mean	SD
ADO1	The orphaned learners are motivated by the project	109(30.03%)	22(6.06%)	22(6.06%)	110(30.30%)	100(27.55%)	3.29	1.59
ADO2	The orphaned learners are not motivated by the project	117(32.23%)	137(37.74%)	32(8.82%)	42(11.57%)	35(9.64%)	2.43	1.28
ADO3	The orphaned learners are appreciated by the project	72(19.84%)	43(11.85%)	38(10.47%)	125(34.44%)	85(23.42%)	3.37	1.39
ADO4	The orphaned learners are	105(29.93%)	107(29.48%)	45(12.40%)	45(12.40%)	61(16.08%)	2.58	1.361

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ADO5	not appreciated by the project The orphaned learners are encouraged by the project	80(22.04%)	50(13.77%)	36(9.92%)	121(33.33%)	76(20.9%)	3.35	1.39
ADO6	The orphaned learners are not encouraged by the project	117(32.23%)	133(36.64%)	27(7.44%)	49(13.50%)	37(10.19%)	2.48	1.314
ADO7	The orphaned learners are praised by the project	81(22.31%)	53(14.60%)	57(15.70%)	104(28.65%)	68(18.73%)	3.30	1.334
ADO8	The orphaned learners are not praised by the project	109(30.03%)	102(28.10%)	59(16.25%)	50(13.77%)	43(11.85%)	2.68	1.33
ADO9	The orphaned learners are valued by the project	86(22.69%)	51(14.05%)	31(8.54%)	113(31.13%)	82(22.59%)	3.42	1.38
ADO10	The orphaned learners are not valued by the project	114(31.41%)	109(30.03%)	55(15.15%)	45(12.40%)	40(11.02%)	2.58	1.32

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics on the Care givers' perspectives on Appreciative Design Orientation on Orphaned Learners' Educational Achievements. Five positively worded statements and five negatively worded statements were used to determine the perspectives of Care givers. ADO1 was positively worded and sought to establish the extent to which care givers agreed, disagreed or were neutral on the statement that orphaned learners are motivated by the project. 109(30.03%) of the care givers strongly disagreed with the statement; 22(6.06%) of the care givers disagreed with the statement; 22(6.06%) were neutral; 110(30.30%) agreed with the statement, while 100(27.7%) strongly agreed with the statement that orphaned learners are motivated by the projects. The mean of ADO1 item was 3.29, with a standard deviation of was 1.59, suggesting that care givers agreed that orphaned learners were motivated by the projects. ADO2 was negatively worded and sought to establish the extent to which care givers agreed, disagreed or were neutral on the statement that orphaned learners are not motivated by the project. 117(32.23%) of the care givers strongly disagreed with the statement; 137(37.74%) disagreed with the statement, 32(8.82%) were neutral, 42(11.57%) agreed with the statement, while 35(9.64%) strongly agreed with the statement. The mean of the statement was 2.43 with s standard deviation of 1.28 suggesting that the care givers disagreed with the statement that orphaned learners are not motivated by the projects.

ADO3 was positively worded and sought to establish the extent to which care givers agreed, disagreed or were neutral on the statement that orphaned learners are appreciated by the project. 72(19.84%) of the care givers strongly disagreed with the statement; 43(11.85%) disagreed with the statement, 38(10.47%) were neutral, 125(34.44%) agreed with the statement, while 85(23.42%) strongly agreed with the statement. The mean of the statement was 3.37 with a standard deviation of 1.39 suggesting that the care givers agreed with the statement that orphaned learners are appreciated by the projects. ADO4 was negatively worded and sought to establish the extent to which care givers agreed, disagreed or were neutral on the statement that orphaned learners are not appreciated by the project. 105(29.93%) of the care givers strongly disagreed with the statement; 107(29.48%) disagreed with the statement, 45(12.40%) were neutral, 45(12.40%) agreed with the statement, while 61(16.08%) strongly agreed with the statement. The mean of the statement was 2.58 with a standard deviation of 1.1361 suggesting that the care givers agreed with the statement that orphaned learners are not appreciated by the projects.

ADO5 was positively worded and sought to establish the extent to which care givers agreed, disagreed or were neutral on the statement that orphaned learners are encouraged by the project. 80(22.04%) of care givers strongly disagreed with the statement; 50(13.77%) disagreed with the statement, 36(9.92%) were neutral, 121(33.33%) agreed with the statement, while 76(20.9%) strongly agreed with the statement. The mean of the statement was 3.35 with a standard deviation of 1.39 suggesting that the care givers agreed with the statement that orphaned learners are encouraged by the projects. ADO6 was negatively worded and sought to establish the extent to which care givers agreed, disagreed or were neutral on the statement that orphaned learners are not encouraged by the project. 117(32.23%) of the care givers strongly disagreed with the statement; 133(36.64%) disagreed with the statement, 27(7.44%) were neutral, 49(13.50%) agreed with the statement, while 37(10.19%) strongly agreed with the statement. The mean of the statement was 2.48 with a standard deviation of 1.314 suggesting that the care givers disagreed with the statement that orphaned learners are not encouraged by the projects.

ADO7 was positively worded and sought to establish the extent to which care givers agreed, disagreed or were neutral on the statement that orphaned learners are praised by the project. 81(22.31%) of the care givers strongly disagreed with the statement; 53(14.60%) disagreed with the statement, 57(15.70%) were neutral, 104(28.65%) agreed with the statement, while 68(18.73%) strongly agreed with the statement. The mean of the statement was 3.30 with a standard deviation of 1.334 suggesting that the care givers agreed with the statement that orphaned learners are praised by the projects. ADO8 was negatively worded and sought to establish the extent to which care givers agreed, disagreed or were neutral on the statement that orphaned learners are not praised by the project. 109(30.03%) of the care givers strongly disagreed with the statement; 102(28.10%) disagreed with the statement, 59(16.25%) were neutral, 50(13.77%) agreed with the statement, while 43(11.85%) strongly agreed with the statement. The mean of the statement was 2.68 with a standard deviation of

1.33 suggesting that the care givers disagreed with the statement that orphaned learners are not praised by the projects.

ADO9 was positively worded and sought to establish the extent to which care givers agreed, disagreed or were neutral on the statement that orphaned learners are valued by the project. 86(22.69%) of care givers strongly disagreed with the statement; 51(4.05%) disagreed with the statement, 31(8.54%) were neutral, 113(31.13%) agreed with the statement, while 82(22.59%) strongly agreed with the statement. The mean of the statement was 3.42 with a standard deviation of 1.38 suggesting that the care givers agreed with the statement that orphaned learners are valued by the projects. ADO10 was negatively worded and sought to establish the extent to which care givers agreed, disagreed or were neutral on the statement that orphaned learners are not valued by the projects. 114(31.41%) of the care givers strongly disagreed with the statement; 109(30.03%) disagreed with the statement, 55(15.15%) were neutral, 45(12.40%) agreed with the statement, while 40(11.02%) strongly agreed with the statement. The mean of the statement was 2.58 with a standard deviation of 1.32 suggesting that the care givers disagreed with the statement that orphaned learners are not valued by the projects.

5.3 Correlation Analysis on Care Givers' Perspectives on Appreciative Design Orientation and Orphaned Learners' Educational Achievements

Pearson product moment correlation coefficient was used in order to establish the existence or non-existence of significance relationship as well as the degree or strength of association between the Appreciative Design Orientation and Orphaned Learners' Educational Achievements, from the perspectives of the care givers. The bivariate correlation through Pearson correlation coefficient was opted for since the data scale was interval in nature.

Table 3: Correlation Statistics on Care Givers' Perspectives on the Influence of Appreciative Design Orientation on Orphaned Learners' Educational Achievements

Correlations of individual statements on Appreciative Design Orientation		Orphaned Learners' Educational Achievements
ADO1: The orphaned learners are motivated by the project	Pearson Correlation	-.136*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.014
	N	363
ADO2: The orphaned learners are not motivated by the project	Pearson Correlation	-.134*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.018
	N	363
ADO3: The orphaned learners are appreciated by the project	Pearson Correlation	-.041
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.465
	N	363
ADO4: The orphaned learners are not appreciated by the project	Pearson Correlation	-.174**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002
	N	363

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ADO5: The orphaned learners are encouraged by the project	Pearson	-.046
	Correlation	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.410
ADO6: The orphaned learners are not encouraged by the project	N	363
	Pearson	-.115*
	Correlation	
ADO7: The orphaned learners are praised by the project	Sig. (2-tailed)	.043
	N	363
	Pearson	-.057
ADO8: The orphaned learners are not praised by the project	Correlation	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.311
	N	363
ADO9: The orphaned learners are valued by the project	Pearson	-.054
	Correlation	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.363
ADO10: The orphaned learners are not valued by the project	N	363
	Pearson	-.048
	Correlation	
Orphaned Learners' Educational Achievements	Sig. (2-tailed)	.398
	N	363
	Pearson	-.174**
	Correlation	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002
	N	363
	Pearson	1
	Correlation	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	
	N	363

Table 3 presents the correlation statistics on care givers' perspectives on Appreciative Design Orientation and Orphaned Learners' Educational Achievements. The correlation output table shows that not all the Appreciative Design Orientation indicators were significantly related (P -values <0.05) against the indicators of Orphaned Learners' Educational Achievements. Similarly, both positively and negatively worded Appreciative Design Orientation indicators were all correlated with Orphaned Learners Educational Achievements. The small p -values ($p<0.05$) implies that there is a significant relationship between appreciative Design Orientation and Orphaned Learners' Educational Achievements, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis that Appreciative Design Orientation does not significantly influence Orphaned Learners' Educational achievements in Homa Bay County. From the research findings, it was safe to suggest that there is a significant relationship between Appreciative Design Orientation and Orphaned Learners' Educational Achievements. The results are consistent with the findings of other studies that found significant relationships between Appreciative Design Orientation and learners' educational achievements.

5.4 Regression Analysis on Care Givers' Perspectives on Appreciative Design Orientation and Orphaned Learners' Educational Achievements

Regression analyses were run on the care givers' perspectives on the influence of Appreciative Design Orientation on Orphaned Learners' Educational Achievements. Table 4 summarises the ANOVA for the regression on the care givers' perspectives on the influence of Appreciative Design Orientation on Orphaned Learners' Educational Achievements. The above ANOVA table provides F-test for the null hypothesis that none of the explanatory variables from Appreciative Design Orientation are related to Orphaned Learners' Educational Achievements.

Table 4: An ANOVA for the Regression on Care Givers' Perspectives on Appreciative Design Orientation and Orphaned Learners' Educational achievements

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	12.866	10	12.866	11.194	.001 ^b
Residual	290.804	353	1.149		
Total	303.671	363			

a. Dependent Variable: Orphaned Learner's Educational Achievements
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Appreciative Design Orientation

The null hypothesis (H₀1: Appreciative Design Orientation does not significantly influence Orphaned Learners' Educational Achievements in Homa Bay County) was rejected since (F(10,353)= 11.1945.265, P -Value <0.05; and so it was safe to suggest that at least one of the explanatory variables is significantly related to the Orphaned Learners' Educational Achievements. The data, based on the perspectives of the care givers, indicate that Appreciative Design Orientation has strong positive influence on the Orphaned Learners' Educational Achievements.

Table 5: Coefficients for the Regression on Care Givers' Perspectives on Appreciative Design Orientation and Orphaned Learners' Educational Achievements

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
(Constant)	2.401	.272		8.830	.000	1.865	2.936
Appreciative Design Orientation	.256	.076	.206	3.346	.001	.105	.406

a. Dependent Variable: Orphaned Learners' Educational Achievements

Table 5 presents the coefficients for the regression on the care givers' perspectives on the influence of Appreciative Design Orientation on Orphaned Learners' Educational Achievements. The data shows that for every unit increase in the score for Appreciative Design Orientation, the score for Orphaned Learners' Educational Achievements would increase by 0.256. The coefficients for the regression had strong positive statistical significance (0.001). The simple linear regression model is $Y=2.401+0.256X_1$, implying that were there no Appreciative Design Orientation, the Orphaned Learners'

Educational Achievements would be 2.401. The data suggests that, according to the care givers, Appreciative Design Orientation positively influences Orphaned Learners' Educational Achievements.

6. Discussion

The objective of this study was to examine the perspectives of care givers on the influence of appreciative project design orientation on the educational achievements of orphaned learners enrolled in orphan support projects in Homa Bay County, Kenya. Appreciative project design orientation, conceptualised as project design approach that appreciates, recognises and positively affirms disadvantaged and vulnerable children (Shier, 2001), is believed to have beneficial influence on a wide range of outcomes, including educational outcomes for disadvantaged and vulnerable children, like the orphaned learners (Shier, 2001; UNICEF, 2008b). From the results of the study, motivation, appreciation, encouragement, praise and valuing of the orphaned learners were found to be important indicators of appreciative design orientation. Care givers in orphan support projects should ensure that appreciative project design approaches are integrated during the design of the projects.

The results of the descriptive statistics on the project managers' perspectives on educational achievements indicate that majority of the care givers strongly agreed that school attendance, participation in co-curricular activities, learner discipline, homework completion and grade progression, were important indicators of orphaned learners' educational achievements. The null hypothesis for the (The null hypothesis (H_0 : Appreciative Design Orientation does not significantly influence Orphaned Learners' Educational Achievements in Homa Bay County) was rejected since ($F(10,353)=11.1945.265$, P -Value <0.05 ; and so it was safe to suggest that at least one of the explanatory variables is significantly related to the Orphaned Learners' Educational Achievements. The data, based on the perspectives of the care givers, indicate that Appreciative Design Orientation has strong positive influence on the Orphaned Learners' Educational Achievements.

7. Conclusions and Recommendations

The governments of Kenya, development partners and community based organizations involved in orphan support programming should ensure the integration of appreciative design orientation and approaches when designing and implementing orphan support projects. The study has demonstrated that appreciative design orientations, approaches and mind sets have significant positive influence on the educational achievements of orphaned learners. The integration of appreciative project design orientation may call for special training and capacity building not just to project designers but also to policy makers, donors and organizations and individuals involved in orphan support programming.

Whereas the educational achievements of orphaned learners is at the heart of orphan support programming, the absence of a documented policy on orphaned learners' educational achievements has affected the realization of the educational achievement goals in orphan support projects. There is strong research evidence that despite the efforts to promote the education of orphaned learners in the country, the achievement gap is still widening. Compared to non-orphaned learners, a number of orphaned learners still have poor educational outcomes. The development and enforcement of educational achievement policy, which is holistic and not just focused on improving test scores and passing examinable subjects, will hopefully reduce and seal the gap. The government of Kenya should ensure the development of an educational achievement policy to be implemented by all stakeholders involved in orphan support programming.

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